

METAPHORICAL MODELS IN POLITICS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6548155>

Muratbayeva Aizhan

M1703-30 group undergraduate

Rizahodjayeva G.A

Supervisor: PhD, Senior Teacher

South Kazakhstan State Pedagogical University, Shymkent

Abstract: *This paper approaches the topic of conceptual metaphor and political communication from a textual-linguistic, semantic, cognitive-linguistic and argumentative perspective. The manner of implementation of conceptual metaphors in the analysed sample is in direct relationship to the text form of Borčić, N., Kanižaj, I., Kršul, S.: Conceptual Metaphor in Political interview. The basic language, or textual function of a political interview is the informative-persuasive function. Political communication presents a form of interaction, i.e. public communication which develops through available linguistic knowledge in the area of political activity. The persuasive effect of political interviews builds on the original feature of rhetoric as the power of persuasion in truthfulness and correctness of what is being said. Issuers, i.e. politicians want to challenge the recipients' own interpretation through the offered conceptual statements. Scientists who deal with language policy and conceptual metaphors in a language find the subtle expression of emotions through the use of metaphor one of the essential characteristics of a successful persuasive political communication. Conceptual metaphors in that way shape the themes of a certain society and also affect social reality by emphasizing certain parts of the theme or approach to the theme. Use of conceptual metaphors makes it possible to point out that part of the target domain to which one wants to direct the attention of the recipient. Leading politicians should know how the nation "breathes" and the language should match the powers that they have and their positions.*

Ever since the ancient times metaphor has been a point of interest for many linguists, writers and philosophers. Since the conceptual metaphor is the topic of this paper, the theoretical framework of the paper included only the theory concerning conceptual metaphors in cognitive linguistics. In doing so, only the part of theory the research is based on is explained. The conceptual metaphor has been researched by cognitive linguistics since 1980. It was then that the original model of George Lakoff and Mark

Johnson came into existence, and their book *Metaphors We Live by* is seen as its starting point. The research in this paper is based on this original theory of the conceptual metaphor within cognitive linguistics developed in the 1980s. Lakoff and Johnson introduced the knowledge of how daily life is interwoven with metaphorical expressions and that metaphorisation is actually fundamental for the understanding of a language. According to them, conceptual metaphors are pervasive in everyday life, not just in language, but in thoughts and actions. In the last 20 years (conceptual) metaphors have become both a trend and a challenge for speechwriters. In recent political discourse politicians throughout the world use metaphors in order to enrich their discourse but also to send their messages to the public and/or voters. The political argument is primarily focused on getting the recipient's partiality in relation to the statement of the issuer. Successful politicians have to be informative but at the same time persuasive. Their language has to be influential because they probably want their messages to be remembered. Lakoff believes that politicians, using metaphors in political issues, set the framework in which voters then think about certain issues.

Lakoff and Johnson divide conceptual metaphors according to their cognitive role into three main groups: structural, ontological and orientational. In structural metaphors, one concept is realized with the help of the other, and the examples of such metaphors are LIFE IS A JOURNEY or TIME IS MONEY. In orientational metaphors, the entire system of terms is organised in relation to the other, such as in the examples HEALTH AND LIFE ARE UP, DISEASE AND DEATH ARE DOWN. Orientational metaphors are based on our physical and cultural experience. Experiences with concrete physical objects, and especially the body, lay a foundation to create an ontological metaphor, which is the third type of metaphors. Ontological metaphors are created either by reification or personification (Charteris-Black, 2005, 15). By using the reification, or the concretization of the abstract event, the actions and emotions become shaped entities or physical objects. Lakoff and Johnson (2004, 36-38) mention THE INFLATION IS THE ENTITY or THE SOUL IS A FRAGILE OBJECT as examples of an ontological metaphor based on reification. Personification is further considered to be the most common ontological metaphor. Appearances, associations, social movements etc. are explained with the help of categories common to people, based on our motivation, goals, activities and characteristics. Personification is an ontological metaphor, which, according to Kövesces "uses for the source domain one of the best,

ourselves". This metaphor is common in the political discourse. It is used to give human characteristics to political parties, institutions or certain events, which influences the development of positive or negative associations in recipients.

There are 3 main groups of metaphorical models in system of political discourse — anthropomorphous, naturemorphous, sociomorphous (social) and artifact.

The anthropomorphous metaphor

The anthropomorphous metaphor is based on comparison of inanimate objects, animals and plants with a human body (Moskvin 1997) and the physiological processes happening in it. The metaphor of a healthy and sick organism in the political text is widely consecrated practically in works of all leading experts on cognitive linguistics: E.V. Budayev (2006), K. Banks (2009), T.S. Vershinina (2002), J. Zavadil (2009), E.V. Kolotnina (2001), J. Lakoff (2004), A. Musolff (2006, 2009), O.A. Solopova (2006), A.P. Chudinov (2001, 2003), E.I. Sheygal (2000) and etc. Models with spheres sources "Human body" which function in the Russian and British political discourse are given in E.V. Budayev's monograph. The author comes to the conclusion that the anthropomorphous metaphorical model "concerns to the most universal... as predetermines small discourse "flexibility" of metaphorical model, low level of frequency variability at change of the sphere-target of metaphorical expansion".

Here some slots from E. Trollope's novel "The Prime Minister":

1. Frame "Body of person in general". Parties and the organizations are designated in the novel as *тело* (*body*), that points to their integrity : ... *however strong might be the Coalition as a body, it was weak as to finance* (90). Nevertheless, Coalition force as uniform organism doesn't guarantee its stability financially.

2. Frame "Parts of body". Conceptual metaphors as a part of this frame are used by the author for representation of political reality subjects' distinctive features.

3. The slot "Integumentary fabric" contains the greatest number of models with the initial sphere skin (skin), thus as the sphere target of a metaphorical attraction parliamentarians act. Depending on a situation and character of the figure, a concept skin gets distinctive connotative signs. The name the thin-skinned contains pragmatic sense of weakness of intentions, indecision, inability to answer criticism: *'Of course there is. And then with zeal there always goes a thin skin,—and unjustifiable expectations, and biting despair, and contempt of others, and all the elements of unhappiness.'* (82);

He was **so thin-skinned** that any counsel offered him took the form of criticism (375) and etc.

Naturemorphic Metaphorical Model

Research of zoomorphism organic conceptual metaphor widely received significant reflection in works of scientists-philologists E.V. Budayev (2006), T.S. Vershinina (2002), E. Petter (2004), M. G. Read (2004), J. Robertson (2008), Y.B. Fedeneeva (1997), A.P. Chudinov (2001) and etc. As show results of supervision, pragmatic potential of biological metaphors, in particular with the sphere source "Fauna", it is capable to form at the addressee a negative image of the politician. A.P. Chudinov notes negative emotional coloring of the majority the zoomorphous conceptual metaphors . Most structured and total characteristic of biological metaphor of the Russian political discourse is shown in dissertation research of T.S. Vershinina "Metaphorical models with the initial biological sphere in modern a political discourse".

It should be noted that Anthony Trollope and Jeffrey Archer resort to an organic metaphor for the expressional and estimated nomination of the British politicians and an imagination of fictional political reality.

Metaphorical models with the sphere source "Fauna" in Anthony Trollope's novel of "The Prime Minister".

In E. Trollope's novel of "The Prime Minister" political events in the British parliament are depicted as animals, eyes of animals, and also through a prism of relationship between the person and representatives of the zoological world. The author uses names of pets, various sea and river inhabitants, birds, insects for conceptualization of images of politicians. The attitudes between politicians are shown in the sphere of interactions of subjects of fauna, thus the pragmatic potential of aggression, rigidity is shown. This model is quite widespread in the novel and totals 40 names.

Frame "Name of an animal". As denotants for the initial sphere source of metaphorical expansion act figures of parliament, the main and minor characters of the novel.

The slot "Pets" make metaphorical models with concepts of dogs, horses, rats, pigs with negative connotative coloring. The image of a dog (puppy) is especially widespread: *The old men said it was because the young men were pretentious puppies (10)*. The pragmatic sense of immaturity put in a metaphor is observed: *'They're both good men in their way, you know.'* - *'But why do they come to me with their mouths open, like dogs craving a bone?'* (53); *'A Duke of Omnium can't want to send the country to the dogs.'... (108); He had... feeling that he oughtn't to run out of*

the borough like a whipt dog (252), etc. The elements accompanying the main concepts strengthen a pragmatic orientation of metaphorical models. In some cases the author doesn't call a source of metaphorical expansion directly, and implicit the name as a part of a metaphorical context: The whisper suggested that falling houses were often left by certain animals... (545). In this example of certain animals (certain animals) are rats who as it is considered to be, the first leave the collapsing designs. As denotes act of metaphors politicians and parliament act.

Sociomorphous Metaphorical Model

According to our supervision, the structure of this group within the studied art political discourse was created as at the expense of the subgroups answering to standard structure according to the theory of metaphorical modeling - "War", "Sport", "Theatre", "The family relations", - and separate groups of metaphorical models of adjacent conceptual spheres [81].

So, for example, in the analyzed A. Trollope's novel the metaphorical model Game goes beyond the Sport model on the quantitative structure. Similar supervision belongs to the Children model in Jeffrey Archer's work making the separate group adjacent to the Family Relations model. In the novel "The Prime Minister" A. Trollope we allocated "monarchic and legal" metaphors, and also the models relating to the sphere of economy, the natural and exact sciences.

Metaphorical models with the sphere-source "War" in Anthony Trollope's novel "The Prime Minister".

Conceptual metaphors with the initial sphere "War" were considered in many researches on cognitive linguistics. Still J. Lakoff and M. Johnson pointed to importance of this metaphor in the context of the American culture (Lakoff, Johnson, 1990) military metaphors in the Russian, American and British political discourse (Baranov, Karaulov 1991, Kaslova 2003; Koller 2003, Lakoff 2004, Musolff 2004, Chudinov 2001, 2003 and etc.).

Metaphorical expressions from the military sphere are widely used in E. Trollope's novel of "The Prime Minister". In the British parliament political fights in interests of this or that party or certain subjects are constantly conducted. Politicians are considered as enemies and allies who will organize campaigns, attack, go to attack, use different types of the weapon. Metaphors of the military sphere contain a vector of aggression and are a powerful tool of impact on reader opinions. The "military" metaphor of A. Trollope totals 65 names.

Frame "War and military operations". The metaphors containing the nominations war, actions concerning the opponent, strategic planning of fight are the cornerstone of this frame.

The slot "War". The concept of war in the novel doesn't possess the expressed aggressive potential — it is war sparring, war at daggers points, but not with use of the heavy weapon. Thus, the author accents the importance of the interpersonal conflicts in the world of policy which can be aggravated, or even to develop into serious fight. *It was very soon known to all the world that there was war to the knife between Lord Drummond and the Prime Minister (493); after that there was some sparring of a very bitter kind between Sir Timothy and Phineas Finn, till at last it seemed that the debate was to degenerate into a war of man against man (550).* In separate examples the author implicit the status of the politician through a war metaphor: *A member of Parliament this Session hadn't been by half so much bigger than another man as in times of hot political warfare (302).*

REFERENCES:

1. Ahrens, K. (ed) (2009), *Politics, Gender and Conceptual Metaphors*, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
2. Cox, J. (2012), *Politics in Motion: Barac Obama's Use of Movement Metaphors*, *American Communication Journal*, 14(2), 1-13.
3. Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. (1980), *Metaphors We Live By*, Chicago: Chicago University Press.
4. Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. (2004), *Leben in Metaphern*, Heidelberg : CarlAuer Systeme.
5. Lakoff, G. (1991), *The Metaphor System Used to Justify War in the Gulf*. *Journal of Urban and Cultural Studies* 2(1), 59-72.
6. Archer J. *First Among Equals* [Текст] / Jeffrey Archer//. Harper Collins Publishers, 1984.-471 P.
7. Jeffrey Archer. *And His Place in Modern British Genre Fiction* [Текст] // English, 2003.- № 32.
8. Jeffrey Archer Art Gallery (Official Site for Jeffrey Archer) [Электронныйресурс] Режимдоступа: [//http://www.iefrevarcherbook5.com/art_galleryv.htm](http://www.iefrevarcherbook5.com/art_galleryv.htm).
9. Anderson, J. R., Jr. *Metaphors of Dictatorship and Democracy: Change in the Russian Political Lexicon and the Transformation of Russian-Politics* [Электронныйресурс] /John R. Anderson-Jr.

10. Mio, J. (1996), *Metaphor, Politics and Persuasion*. Mio, J. (ed.), Katz, A. (ed.) *Metaphor: Implications and Applications*, Mahwah: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 127–147.
11. Musolff, A. (2004), *Metaphor and Political Discourse: Analogical Reasoning in Debates about Europe*, Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.